

CONSTRAINT-PRECONDITIONED KRYLOV SOLVERS FOR REGULARIZED SADDLE-POINT SYSTEMS

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Abstract. We consider the iterative solution of regularized saddle-point systems. When the leading block is symmetric and positive semi-definite on an appropriate subspace, [Dollar, Gould, Schilders, and Wathen \(2006\)](#) describe how to apply the conjugate gradient (CG) method coupled with a constraint preconditioner, a choice that has proved to be effective in optimization applications. We investigate the design of constraint-preconditioned variants of other Krylov methods for regularized systems by focusing on the underlying basis-generation process. We build upon principles laid out by [Gould, Orban, and Rees \(2014\)](#) to provide general guidelines that allow us to specialize any Krylov method to regularized saddle-point systems. In particular, we obtain constraint-preconditioned variants of Lanczos and Arnoldi-based methods, including the Lanczos version of CG, MINRES, SYMMLQ, GMRES(ℓ) and DQGMRES. We also provide MATLAB implementations in hopes that they are useful as a basis for the development of more sophisticated software. Finally, we illustrate the numerical behavior of constraint-preconditioned Krylov solvers using symmetric and nonsymmetric systems arising from constrained optimization.

Key words. Regularized saddle-point systems, constraint preconditioners, Lanczos and Arnoldi procedures, Krylov solvers.

AMS subject classifications. 65F08, 65F10, 65F50, 90C20.

1. Introduction. We consider the iterative solution of the regularized saddle-point system

$$(1) \quad \begin{bmatrix} A & B^T \\ B & -C \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} b \\ 0 \end{bmatrix},$$

where $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ may be nonsymmetric, $C \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$ is nonzero and symmetric, and $B \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$. We denote K the matrix of (1). There is no loss of generality in assuming that the last m entries of the right-hand side of (1) are zero, as discussed later.

A constraint preconditioner for (1) has the form

$$(2) \quad P = \begin{bmatrix} G & B^T \\ B & -C \end{bmatrix},$$

where G is an approximation to A such that (2) is nonsingular. When A is symmetric and has appropriate additional properties, a constraint preconditioner allows the application of CG even though K and P are indefinite ([Dollar et al., 2006](#)).

We are interested in the design of constraint-preconditioned versions of additional Krylov methods for (1), including methods that can be used when A is nonsymmetric. We extend the work of [Gould et al. \(2014\)](#) on projected and constraint-preconditioned Krylov methods for saddle-point systems with $C = 0$ by exploiting a suitable reformulation of (1) suggested by [Dollar et al. \(2006\)](#). We develop constraint-preconditioned

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36 variants of the Lanczos and Arnoldi basis-generation processes, and use them to
 37 derive variants of Krylov solvers based on those processes. More generally, we provide
 38 guidelines that can be also exploited to obtain constraint-preconditioned versions of
 39 other Krylov methods not considered in this paper. Finally, we distribute MATLAB
 40 implementations of the constraint-preconditioned methods discussed here as templates
 41 for the development of more sophisticated numerical software.

42 Systems of type (1) arise in interior-point methods for constrained optimization
 43 in the presence of inequality constraints or when regularization is used (Benzi, Golub,
 44 and Liesen, 2005; D’Apuzzo, De Simone, and di Serafino, 2010; Friedlander and Orban,
 45 2012). They also appear in Lagrangian approaches for variational problems with
 46 equality constraints when the constraints are relaxed or a penalty term is applied
 47 (Pestana and Wathen, 2015). In the above cases, A is usually symmetric, but may also
 48 be nonsymmetric—see Section 7, and often has additional properties, e.g., it accounts
 49 for local convexity of the optimization problem. Regularized saddle-point systems with
 50 nonsymmetric A arise also from the stabilized finite-element discretization of Oseen
 51 problems obtained by linearization, through Picard’s method, of the steady-state
 52 Navier-Stokes equations governing the flow of a Newtonian incompressible viscous
 53 fluid (Benzi et al., 2005).

54 Constraint preconditioners have widely demonstrated their effectiveness on saddle-
 55 point systems, especially when the leading block is symmetric and enjoys additional
 56 properties, such as being positive definite; much work has been carried out to develop,
 57 analyze and approximate constraint preconditioners in this case, see, e.g., (Benzi et al.,
 58 2005; D’Apuzzo et al., 2010; Gould et al., 2014; De Simone, di Serafino, and Morini,
 59 2018) and the references therein.

60 The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 provides preliminary
 61 results used in the sequel. In Section 3, we describe the constraint-preconditioned
 62 Lanczos process and, in Section 4, we present variants of Krylov solvers based on it.
 63 In Section 5, we describe the constraint-preconditioned Arnoldi process and associated
 64 Krylov methods. In Section 6, we discuss implementation issues and provide details
 65 on the MATLAB codes. In Section 7, we illustrate the numerical behavior of some
 66 constraint-preconditioned solvers on regularized saddle-point systems, with symmetric
 67 and nonsymmetric matrices, from constrained optimization. We conclude in Section 8.

68 **Notation.** Uppercase Latin letters (A, B, \dots), lowercase Latin letters (a, b, \dots),
 69 and lowercase Greek letters (α, β, \dots) denote matrices, vectors and scalars, respectively.
 70 The Euclidean norm is denoted $\|\cdot\|$. If $S = S^T$ is a positive definite matrix, the
 71 S -norm is defined as $\|u\|_S^2 = u^T S u$. All vectors are column vectors. For any vector
 72 v , $\text{diag}(v)$ is the diagonal matrix with diagonal entries equal to the entries of v . For
 73 brevity, we use the MATLAB-like notation $[v; w]$ to represent the vector $[v^T w^T]^T$.

74 **2. Preliminaries.** We assume throughout that K is nonsingular, which implies

$$75 \quad (3) \quad \text{Null}(A) \cap \text{Null}(B) = \{0\} \quad \text{and} \quad \text{Null}(B^T) \cap \text{Null}(C) = \{0\}.$$

In general the converse is not true. A counterexample consists in taking

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad B = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad C = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}.$$

76 Benzi et al. (2005) and D’Apuzzo et al. (2010) give additional conditions that guarantee
 77 nonsingularity of K . Note however that we do not require B to have full rank or C to
 78 be positive (semi-)definite.

In order to develop constraint-preconditioned Krylov methods for (1), we specialize the basis-generation processes underlying those methods. We focus on the Lanczos (1950) and Arnoldi (1951) processes, which compute orthonormal bases of Krylov spaces associated with symmetric and general matrices, respectively. For reference, the preconditioned Lanczos process is stated as Algorithm 4 in Appendix A. The standard Lanczos process follows by setting the preconditioner to the identity. It is straightforward to apply our arguments to the Lanczos (1950) biorthogonalization process and its transpose-free variants (Brezinski and Redivo-Zaglia, 1998; Chan, de Pillis, and van der Vorst, 1998). We implicitly assume that $A = A^T$ when considering the Lanczos process.

Following Dollar et al. (2006), we reformulate (1) as follows. Assume that $\text{rank}(C) = p$ and C has been decomposed as¹

$$(4) \quad C = EFE^T,$$

where $F \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times p}$ is symmetric and nonsingular and $E \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times p}$. Then, by using the auxiliary variable

$$(5) \quad w = -FE^T y,$$

equation (1) may be written

$$(6) \quad \begin{bmatrix} A & & B^T \\ & F^{-1} & E^T \\ B & E & \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ w \\ y \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} b \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix},$$

which has a standard symmetric saddle-point form

$$(7) \quad \begin{bmatrix} M & N^T \\ N & \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} g \\ y \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} b_0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad M = \begin{bmatrix} A & \\ & F^{-1} \end{bmatrix}, \quad N = [B \quad E], \quad g = \begin{bmatrix} x \\ w \end{bmatrix}, \quad b_0 = \begin{bmatrix} b \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

The principles laid out by Gould et al. (2014) may now be applied to (6).

Note that (6) is nonsingular if and only if (1) is nonsingular, and therefore N must have full rank. Because $g \in \text{Null}(N)$, there exists $\hat{d} \in \mathbb{R}^{n+p-m}$ such that

$$(8) \quad g = \begin{bmatrix} x \\ w \end{bmatrix} = Z \hat{d} = \begin{bmatrix} Z_1 \\ Z_2 \end{bmatrix} \hat{d},$$

where the columns of Z form a basis of $\text{Null}(N)$. The restriction of (6) to $\text{Null}(N)$ is

$$(9) \quad \widehat{M} \hat{x} = \hat{b},$$

where

$$(10a) \quad \widehat{M} = Z^T M Z = Z_1^T A Z_1 + Z_2^T F^{-1} Z_2,$$

$$(10b) \quad \begin{bmatrix} x \\ w \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Z_1 \\ Z_2 \end{bmatrix} \hat{x}, \quad \hat{b} = [Z_1^T \quad Z_2^T] \begin{bmatrix} b \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = Z_1^T b.$$

In a Krylov method for (9), it is appropriate to use a preconditioner of the form

$$(11) \quad \widehat{P} = Z_1^T G Z_1 + Z_2^T F^{-1} Z_2.$$

¹Note that (4) will be only used for the purpose of deriving computational processes and need not be computed in practice.

110 If G is suitable, the preconditioned method can be reformulated entirely in terms of
 111 full space quantities (Gould, Hribar, and Nocedal, 2001; Dollar et al., 2006; Gould
 112 et al., 2014). Following (Gould et al., 2014, Assumption 2.2), we require the following
 113 assumption.

ASSUMPTION 2.1. *The matrix*

$$\begin{bmatrix} G & \\ & F^{-1} \end{bmatrix}$$

114 *is symmetric and positive definite on $\text{Null}(N)$.*

115 A consequence of Assumption 2.1 is that (11) is symmetric and positive definite.

116 We enforce Assumption 2.1 throughout this paper to guarantee that Krylov
 117 methods for (9) give rise to corresponding full-space methods for (1). However, at
 118 least in principle, Assumption 2.1 is not always necessary, e.g., in Krylov methods
 119 based on the Arnoldi process.

120 The application of the preconditioner \hat{P} , i.e., $\check{u} = \hat{P}^{-1}\hat{u}$, can be written as

$$121 \quad (12) \quad \begin{bmatrix} \bar{u}_x \\ \bar{u}_w \end{bmatrix} = P_G \begin{bmatrix} u_x \\ u_w \end{bmatrix}, \quad P_G = Z\hat{P}^{-1}Z^T, \quad \begin{bmatrix} \bar{u}_x \\ \bar{u}_w \end{bmatrix} = Z\check{u}, \quad Z^T \begin{bmatrix} u_x \\ u_w \end{bmatrix} = \hat{u}.$$

Furthermore,

$$P_G \begin{bmatrix} G & \\ & F^{-1} \end{bmatrix}$$

122 is an oblique projector into $\text{Null}(N)$. Let \hat{L} be the lower triangular Cholesky factor of
 123 \hat{P} and let

$$124 \quad (13) \quad \hat{\mathcal{K}} = \mathcal{K} \left(\hat{L}^{-1}\hat{M}\hat{L}^{-T}, \hat{L}^{-1}(\hat{b} - \hat{M}\hat{x}_0) \right)$$

125 be the Krylov space generated by the preconditioned reduced operator $\hat{L}^{-1}\hat{M}\hat{L}^{-T}$
 126 and initial vector $\hat{L}^{-1}(\hat{b} - \hat{M}\hat{x}_0)$, where \hat{b} is given in (10) and $x_0 = Z_1\hat{x}_0$, with Z_1
 127 defined in (8).

128 The computation of (12) can be obtained by solving

$$129 \quad (14) \quad \begin{bmatrix} G & & B^T \\ & F^{-1} & E^T \\ B & E & \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \bar{u}_x \\ \bar{u}_w \\ \bar{z} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} u_x \\ u_w \\ 0 \end{bmatrix},$$

130 see, e.g., Gould et al. (2001), so that P_G could be expressed as

$$131 \quad P_G = \begin{bmatrix} I & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & I & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} G & & B^T \\ & F^{-1} & E^T \\ B & E & \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} I & 0 \\ 0 & I \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

132 We now apply Principles 2.1 and 2.2 of Gould et al. (2014) to the standard Lanczos
 133 basis-generation process for $\hat{\mathcal{K}}$, and obtain the projected Lanczos process outlined in
 134 Algorithm 1.

135 In Algorithm 1, the notation $\|u\|_{[P]}$ represents a measure of the deviation of
 136 $u = [u_x; u_w]$ from $\text{Null}(N)$ (Gould et al., 2014, Section 3). More precisely

$$137 \quad (15) \quad \|u\|_{[P]}^2 := u_x^T \bar{u}_x + u_w^T \bar{u}_w,$$

Algorithm 1 Projected Lanczos Process

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1: choose  $[x_0; w_0]$  such that  $Bx_0 + Ew_0 = 0$  initial guess
2:  $v_{0,x} = 0, v_{0,w} = -w_0$  initial Lanczos vector
3:  $u_{0,x} = b - Ax_0, u_{0,w} = -F^{-1}w_0$   $u_0 = b_0 - Mg_0$ 
4:  $[\bar{u}_{1,x}; \bar{u}_{1,w}; \bar{z}_1] \leftarrow$  solution of (14) with right-hand side  $[u_{0,x}; u_{0,w}; 0]$ 
5:  $v_{1,x} = \bar{u}_{1,x}, v_{1,w} = \bar{u}_{1,w}$   $v_1 = P_G u_0$ 
6:  $\beta_1 = (v_{1,x}^T u_{0,x} + v_{1,w}^T u_{0,w})^{\frac{1}{2}}$   $\beta_1 = (v_1^T u_0)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ 
7: if  $\beta_1 \neq 0$  then
8:    $v_{1,x} = v_{1,x}/\beta_1, v_{1,w} = v_{1,w}/\beta_1$   $\|v_1\|_{[P]} = 1$ 
9: end if
10:  $k = 1$ 
11: while  $\beta_k \neq 0$  do
12:    $u_{k,x} = Av_{k,x}, u_{k,w} = F^{-1}v_{k,w}$   $u_k = Mv_k$ 
13:    $\alpha_k = v_{k,x}^T u_{k,x} + v_{k,w}^T u_{k,w}$   $\alpha_k = v_k^T u_k$ 
14:    $[\bar{u}_{k+1,x}; \bar{u}_{k+1,w}; \bar{z}_{k+1}] \leftarrow$  solution of (14) with right-hand side  $[u_{k,x}; u_{k,w}; 0]$ 
15:    $v_{k+1,x} = \bar{u}_{k+1,x} - \alpha_k v_{k,x} - \beta_k v_{k-1,x}$   $v_{k+1} = \bar{u}_{k+1} - \alpha_k v_k - \beta_k v_{k-1}$ 
16:    $v_{k+1,w} = \bar{u}_{k+1,w} - \alpha_k v_{k,w} - \beta_k v_{k-1,w}$ 
17:    $\beta_{k+1} = (v_{k+1,x}^T u_{k,x} + v_{k+1,w}^T u_{k,w})^{\frac{1}{2}}$   $\beta_{k+1} = (v_{k+1}^T u_k)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ 
18:   if  $\beta_{k+1} \neq 0$  then
19:      $v_{k+1,x} = v_{k+1,x}/\beta_{k+1}, v_{k+1,w} = v_{k+1,w}/\beta_{k+1}$   $\|v_{k+1}\|_{[P]} = 1$ 
20:   end if
21:    $k = k + 1$ 
22: end while

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where $\bar{u} = [\bar{u}_x; \bar{u}_w]$ is defined by (14). Note that $\|u\|_{[P]}$ is actually a seminorm and vanishes if and only if $[u_x; u_w]$ is orthogonal to $\text{Null}(N)$.

Conceptually, the Lanczos process corresponding to Algorithm 1 can be summarized as

$$\begin{bmatrix} A & & B^T \\ & F^{-1} & E^T \\ B & E & \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} V_{k,x} \\ V_{k,w} \\ \bar{Z}_k \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} G & & B^T \\ & F^{-1} & E^T \\ B & E & \end{bmatrix} \left(\begin{bmatrix} V_{k,x} \\ V_{k,w} \\ \bar{Z}_k \end{bmatrix} T_k + \beta_{k+1} \begin{bmatrix} v_{k+1,x} \\ v_{k+1,w} \\ \bar{z}_{k+1} \end{bmatrix} e_k^T \right),$$

where

$$V_{k,x} = [v_{1,x} \ \dots \ v_{k,x}], \quad V_{k,w} = [v_{1,w} \ \dots \ v_{k,w}], \quad \bar{Z}_k = [\bar{z}_1 \ \dots \ \bar{z}_k],$$

and T_k is the usual Lanczos tridiagonal matrix. Provided that $[x_0; w_0] \in \text{Null}(N)$, (Gould et al., 2014, Theorem 2.2) guarantees that Algorithm 1 is well defined and equivalent to Algorithm 4 in Appendix A applied to (9)–(10) with preconditioner (11). In Algorithm 1 and subsequent algorithms, we use the symbol “ \leftarrow ” to assign to the vector on the left of the arrow the result of the external procedure on the right of the arrow.

In the next sections we show how the projected basis-generation procedures can be further reformulated by referring to the original system (1), thus avoiding the use of E and F and the factorization (4).

154 **3. Constraint-Preconditioned Lanczos Process.** If we define $\bar{p}_k = \bar{u}_{k,x}$ for
155 all $k \geq 1$, and

$$156 \quad (16) \quad t_k = EFu_{k,w}, \quad k = 0, 1, \dots$$

157 then (14) at line 14 of Algorithm 1 can be written as

$$158 \quad (17) \quad \begin{bmatrix} G & B^T \\ B & -C \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \bar{p}_{k+1} \\ \bar{z}_{k+1} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} u_{k,x} \\ -t_k \end{bmatrix}.$$

159 **Assumption 2.1** occurs when the sum of the number of negative eigenvalues of the
160 matrix of (17) and C is m (Dollar et al., 2006, Theorem 2.1), which may be verified if
161 an inertia-revealing symmetric indefinite factorization is used to solve (17), such as
162 that of Duff (2004).

163 Unfortunately, (17) still appears to depend on F via (16). We now reformulate
164 Algorithm 1 in terms of full-space quantities. Define the initial guess

$$165 \quad (18) \quad w_0 = -FE^T q_0,$$

166 where $q_0 \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is arbitrary (e.g., $q_0 = 0$). Line 3 of Algorithm 1 and (16) yield

$$167 \quad u_{0,x} = r_0 = b - Ax_0, \quad u_{0,w} = E^T q_0, \quad t_0 = Cq_0.$$

168 From here on, let us denote $p_k = v_{k,x}$. At lines 4-5 of Algorithm 1, we compute $p_1 = \bar{p}_1$
169 and \bar{z}_1 from (14), which yields, in particular, $\bar{u}_{1,w} = FE^T(q_0 - \bar{z}_1)$. If we define

$$170 \quad s_1 = q_0 - \bar{z}_1, \quad q_1 = s_1,$$

171 lines 5-6 of Algorithm 1 take the form

$$172 \quad (19a) \quad p_1 = \bar{p}_1$$

$$173 \quad (19b) \quad v_{1,w} = FE^T q_1,$$

$$174 \quad (19c) \quad \beta_1 = (p_1^T u_{0,x} + q_1^T Cq_1)^{\frac{1}{2}} = (p_1^T u_{0,x} + q_1^T t_0)^{\frac{1}{2}}.$$

176 We then normalize by dividing p_1 and q_1 by β_1 . Lines 12-13 of Algorithm 1 and (16)
177 give

$$178 \quad (20a) \quad u_{1,w} = E^T q_1,$$

$$179 \quad (20b) \quad t_1 = Cq_1,$$

$$180 \quad (20c) \quad \alpha_1 = p_1^T u_{1,x} + q_1^T t_1 = p_1^T Ap_1 + q_1^T Cq_1.$$

182 We now compute p_2 and $v_{2,w}$ from lines 15-16 of Algorithm 1 with $k = 1$, i.e., we
183 compute \bar{p}_2 and \bar{z}_2 from (17), and note that $\bar{u}_{2,w} = FE^T(q_1 - \bar{z}_2)$. Thus, by setting

$$184 \quad s_2 = q_1 - \bar{z}_2, \quad q_2 = s_2 - \alpha_1 q_1 - \beta_1 q_0,$$

185 we obtain from lines 2 and 15-16 of Algorithm 1 together with (19b), (20a) and (20b):

$$186 \quad p_2 = \bar{p}_2 - \alpha_1 p_1 - \beta_1 p_0$$

$$187 \quad v_{2,w} = FE^T s_2 - \alpha_1 FE^T q_1 - \beta_1 FE^T q_0 = FE^T q_2$$

$$188 \quad \beta_2 = (p_2^T Ap_1 + q_2^T Cq_1)^{\frac{1}{2}} = (p_2^T u_{1,x} + q_2^T t_1)^{\frac{1}{2}}.$$

190 Then, according to line 19, p_2 must be divided by β_2 , and we do the same with q_2 .
 191 An induction argument shows that for all $k \geq 1$

$$\begin{aligned} 192 \quad u_{k,w} &= E^T q_k, \\ 193 \quad t_k &= Cq_k, \\ 194 \quad \alpha_k &= p_k^T u_{k,x} + q_k^T t_k = p_k^T Ap_k + q_k^T Cq_k, \end{aligned}$$

196 where q_k has been normalized by β_k . Furthermore, letting

$$197 \quad s_{k+1} = q_k - \bar{z}_{k+1}, \quad q_{k+1} = s_{k+1} - \alpha_k q_k - \beta_k q_{k-1},$$

198 we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} 199 \quad p_{k+1} &= \bar{p}_{k+1} - \alpha_k p_k - \beta_k p_{k-1} \\ 200 \quad v_{k+1,w} &= FE^T q_{k+1}, \\ 201 \quad \beta_{k+1} &= (p_{k+1}^T Ap_k + q_{k+1}^T Cq_k)^{\frac{1}{2}} = (p_{k+1}^T u_{k,x} + q_{k+1}^T t_k)^{\frac{1}{2}}. \end{aligned}$$

203 We divide p_{k+1} and q_{k+1} by β_{k+1} to obtain the vectors to be used at the next iteration.
 204 Thus, if we rename $u_{k,x}$ as u_k , we obtain [Algorithm 2](#).

Algorithm 2 Constraint-Preconditioned Lanczos Process

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1: choose  $[x_0; q_0]$  such that  $Bx_0 - Cq_0 = 0$  initial guess
2:  $p_0 = 0$  initial Lanczos vector
3:  $u_0 = b - Ax_0$ ,  $t_0 = Cq_0$ 
4:  $[\bar{p}_1; \bar{z}_1] \leftarrow$  solution of (17) with right-hand side  $[u_0; -t_0]$ 
5:  $p_1 = \bar{p}_1$ 
6:  $s_1 = q_0 - \bar{z}_1$ ,  $q_1 = s_1$ 
7:  $\beta_1 = (p_1^T u_0 + q_1^T t_0)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ 
8: if  $\beta_1 \neq 0$  then
9:    $p_1 = p_1/\beta_1$ ,  $q_1 = q_1/\beta_1$ 
10: end if
11:  $k = 1$ 
12: while  $\beta_k \neq 0$  do
13:    $u_k = Ap_k$ ,  $t_k = Cq_k$ 
14:    $\alpha_k = p_k^T u_k + q_k^T t_k$   $= p_k^T Ap_k + q_k^T Cq_k$ 
15:    $[\bar{p}_{k+1}; \bar{z}_{k+1}] \leftarrow$  solution of (17) with right-hand side  $[u_k; -t_k]$ 
16:    $p_{k+1} = \bar{p}_{k+1} - \alpha_k p_k - \beta_k p_{k-1}$ 
17:    $s_{k+1} = q_k - \bar{z}_{k+1}$ ,  $q_{k+1} = s_{k+1} - \alpha_k q_k - \beta_k q_{k-1}$ 
18:    $\beta_{k+1} = (p_{k+1}^T u_k + q_{k+1}^T t_k)^{\frac{1}{2}}$   $= (p_{k+1}^T Ap_k + q_{k+1}^T Cq_k)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ 
19:   if  $\beta_{k+1} \neq 0$  then
20:      $p_{k+1} = p_{k+1}/\beta_{k+1}$ ,  $q_{k+1} = q_{k+1}/\beta_{k+1}$ 
21:   end if
22:    $k = k + 1$ 
23: end while

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205 The above transformations can be condensed in the following principle, which
 206 summarizes the conversion a of projected process into a constraint-preconditioned
 207 process.

208 PRINCIPLE 1.

- 209 1. Basis vectors $v_{k+1,x}$ are unchanged;
 210 2. Basis vectors $v_{k+1,w}$ have the form $FE^T q_{k+1}$, where q_{k+1} is defined by

$$\begin{aligned} 211 \quad s_{k+1} &= q_k - \bar{z}_{k+1}, \\ 212 \quad q_1 &= s_1, \\ 213 \quad q_{k+1} &= s_{k+1} - \alpha_k q_k - \beta_k q_{k-1}, \quad (k \geq 1), \end{aligned}$$

215 and where \bar{z}_{k+1} results from the solution of (17);

- 216 3. Inner products of the form $v_{i,w}^T u_{j,w}$ become $q_i^T C q_j = q_i^T t_j$.

217 **Theorem 1** summarizes the equivalence between the two formulations.

THEOREM 1. Let E and F be as defined in (4) and G chosen to satisfy *Assumption 2.1*. Let $q_0 \in \mathbb{R}^m$ be arbitrary. Then, *Algorithm 1* with starting guesses $x_0 \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and $w_0 = -FE^T q_0$, such that $Bx_0 + Ew_0$, is equivalent to *Algorithm 2* with starting guesses x_0 and q_0 . In particular, for all k , the vectors $v_{k,x}$ and $v_{k,w}$, and the scalars α_k and β_k in *Algorithm 1* are equal to the vectors p_k and $FE^T q_k$, and to the scalars α_k and β_k in *Algorithm 2*, respectively.

218 Note that *Algorithm 2* does not contain references to E and F . The variable s_k
 219 is used only to improve readability. *Assumption 2.1* guarantees that *Algorithm 2* is
 220 well posed because it is equivalent to *Algorithm 1*, which, in turn, is equivalent to
 221 the standard Lanczos process for building an orthonormal basis of (13). The main
 222 advantages of *Algorithm 2* are that it works directly with the formulation (1) and it
 223 only requires storage for three vectors of size $n + m$ ($[p_k; q_k]$, $[u_k; t_k]$, and $[\bar{p}_k; \bar{z}_k]$),
 224 as opposed to the same number of vectors of size $n + p + m$ for *Algorithm 1*.

225 We call *Algorithm 2* the Constraint-Preconditioned Lanczos (CP-Lanczos) process
 226 because of its similarity to a Lanczos process for building an orthonormal basis of a
 227 Krylov space associated with the preconditioned operator $P^{-1}M$, even though the
 228 latter appears nonsymmetric.

229 **4. Constraint-Preconditioned Lanczos-Based Krylov Solvers.** We may
 230 exploit *Theorem 1* and use *Algorithm 2* to derive a constraint-preconditioned version
 231 of any Krylov method based on the Lanczos process. To this aim, we must understand
 232 how the update of the k -th iterate $[x_k; w_k]$ in a Krylov method based on *Algorithm 1*
 233 translates into the update of the k -th iterate $[x_k; y_k]$ in the version of that Krylov
 234 method based on *Algorithm 2*. In the following, the former and the latter version
 235 of the Krylov method are referred to as projected-Krylov (P-Krylov) and constraint-
 236 preconditioned-Krylov (CP-Krylov), respectively.

237 Because the initial guess $g_0 = [x_0; w_0]$ of P-Krylov applied to (6) must lie in
 238 $\text{Null}(N)$, CP-Krylov must be initialized with $[x_0; y_0]$ such that

$$239 \quad (21) \quad Bx_0 - Cy_0 = 0.$$

240 Our first result states a property of *Algorithm 2* that follows from a specific q_0 .

LEMMA 1. Let *Algorithm 2* be initialized with $x_0 \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and $q_0 \in \text{Null}(C)$. Then, for all $k \geq 0$,

$$241 \quad (22) \quad Bp_k + Cq_k = 0.$$

242 *Proof.* We proceed by induction. For $k = 0$, (22) holds because $p_0 = 0$ and
 $q_0 \in \text{Null}(C)$. For $k = 1$, $p_1 = \bar{p}_1$, $q_1 = q_0 - \bar{z}_1 = -\bar{z}_1$, and (17) and our assumption

243 that $q_0 \in \text{Null}(C)$ yield

$$244 \quad Bp_1 + Cq_1 = B\bar{p}_1 - C\bar{z}_1 = -t_0 = -Cq_0 = 0.$$

245 Assume (22) holds for any index $j \leq k$. Lines 16–17 of Algorithm 2, (16), (17), and
246 our induction assumption imply that

$$\begin{aligned} 247 \quad Bp_{k+1} + Cq_{k+1} &= B\bar{p}_{k+1} + C(q_k - \bar{z}_{k+1}) - \alpha_k(Bp_k + Cq_k) - \beta_k(Bp_{k-1} + Cq_{k-1}) \\ 248 \quad &= B\bar{p}_{k+1} + C(q_k - \bar{z}_{k+1}) \\ 249 \quad &= B\bar{p}_{k+1} - C\bar{z}_{k+1} + t_k = 0, \end{aligned}$$

251 which establishes (22). \square

252 An interesting property of the CP-Lanczos process is that it is equivalent to
253 formally applying the standard Lanczos process to system (1) with preconditioner (2),
254 where by “formal application”, we mean that the Lanczos process is applied blindly
255 as if P were positive definite. Such formal application is stated as Algorithm 5 in
256 Appendix A. The equivalence with Algorithm 2 is stated in the next result, which
257 parallels (Gould et al., 2014, Theorem 2.2).

THEOREM 2. *Let Algorithm 2 be initialized with $x_0 \in \mathbb{R}^n$ such that $Bx_0 = 0$,
 $q_0 = 0 \in \mathbb{R}^m$, and Algorithm 5 be initialized with the same x_0 and $y_0 \in \mathbb{R}^m$ such
that (21) is satisfied. Then, for all $k \geq 0$, $v_{k,x} = p_k$ and $v_{k,y} = -q_k$, where
 $[v_{k,x}; v_{k,y}]$ is the k -th Lanczos vector generated in Algorithm 5, and p_k and q_k
are the k -th Lanczos vectors generated in Algorithm 2. In addition, the scalars α_k
and β_k computed at each iteration are the same in both algorithms.*

258 *Proof.* We proceed by induction. The result holds for $k = 0$ because $[v_{0,x}; v_{0,y}] =$
259 $[0; 0] = [p_0; -q_0]$. With $q_0 = 0$, Algorithm 2 initializes $u_0 = b - Ax_0$ and $t_0 = 0$.
260 Because (21) is satisfied, Algorithm 5 initializes $r_{0,x} = u_0 - B^T y_0$ and $r_{0,y} = 0$. Thus,
261 $[v_{1,x}; v_{1,y}]$ solves (17) with right-hand side $[u_0 - B^T y_0; 0]$. By (Gould et al., 2014,
262 Theorem 2.1, item 2), $[v_{1,x}; v_{1,y}]$ equivalently solves (17) with right-hand side $[u_0; 0]$,
263 and therefore, $[v_{1,x}; v_{1,y}]$ at line 4 of Algorithm 5 is equal to $[\bar{p}_1; \bar{z}_1]$. Lines 5–6 of
264 Algorithm 2 subsequently set $p_1 = \bar{p}_1 = v_{1,x}$ and $q_1 = s_1 = q_0 - \bar{z}_1 = -v_{1,y}$.

265 With $q_0 = 0$, line 7 of Algorithm 2 computes $\beta_1 = (p_1^T u_0)^{\frac{1}{2}}$. We take the inner
266 product of the second row of (17) with $\bar{z}_1 = -q_1$ and note that $t_0 = 0$, and obtain
267 $\bar{z}_1^T Bp_1 = \bar{z}_1^T C\bar{z}_1 = q_1^T Cq_1$. Similarly, we take the inner product of the first row of (17)
268 with p_1 and substitute $\bar{z}_1^T Bp_1$ to obtain $p_1^T u_0 = p_1^T Gp_1 + q_1^T Cq_1$, so that β_1 is the
269 same as that computed at line 5 of Algorithm 5. We have established that the result
270 also holds for $k = 1$.

271 At a general iteration k , Algorithm 2 sets $u_k = Ap_k$, $t_k = Cq_k$ and computes
272 $\alpha_k = p_k^T u_k + q_k^T t_k = p_k^T Ap_k + q_k^T Cq_k$. By Lemma 1, $q_k^T Bp_k + q_k^T Cq_k = 0$, so that
273 $\alpha_k = p_k^T Ap_k - 2q_k^T Bp_k - q_k^T Cq_k$. Under the recurrence assumption that $v_{k,x} = p_k$
274 and $v_{k,y} = -q_k$, this expression of α_k is the same as that computed at line 12 of
275 Algorithm 5.

276 At line 15 of Algorithm 2, we compute $[\bar{p}_{k+1}; \bar{z}_{k+1}]$ from (17), or, equivalently, as
277 the solution to

$$278 \quad \begin{bmatrix} G & B^T \\ B & -C \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \bar{p}_{k+1} \\ \bar{z}_{k+1} - q_k \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Ap_k \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

279 In view of Lemma 1, our recurrence assumption, and (Gould et al., 2014, Theorem 2.1,
280 item 2), line 13 of Algorithm 5 computes $[v_{k+1,x}; v_{k+1,y}]$ as the solution to the

same system as above. Therefore, at that point in each algorithm $v_{k+1,x} = \bar{p}_{k+1}$ and $v_{k+1,y} = \bar{z}_{k+1} - q_k = -s_{k+1}$. The vector updates at lines 16–17 of Algorithm 2 together with those at line 14 of Algorithm 5 show that $v_{k+1,x} = p_{k+1}$ and $v_{k+1,y} = -q_{k+1}$. Our recurrence assumption and Lemma 1 yield $Bv_{k,x} - Cv_{k,y} = 0$ and $Bv_{k+1,x} - Cv_{k+1,y} = 0$. Finally, Algorithm 5 sets

$$\begin{aligned} \beta_{k+1}^2 &= v_{k+1,x}^T u_{k,x} + v_{k+1,y}^T u_{k,y} \\ &= v_{k+1,x}^T A v_{k,x} + (Bv_{k+1,x} - Cv_{k+1,y})^T v_{k,y} + v_{k+1,y}^T B v_{k,x} \\ &= v_{k+1,x}^T A v_{k,x} + v_{k+1,y}^T C v_{k,x}, \end{aligned}$$

which is the same value computed in Algorithm 2. \square

Theorem 2 shows that Algorithm 2 may be summarized as

$$\begin{bmatrix} A & B^T \\ B & -C \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} P_k \\ -Q_k \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} G & B^T \\ B & -C \end{bmatrix} \left(\begin{bmatrix} P_k \\ -Q_k \end{bmatrix} T_k + \beta_{k+1} \begin{bmatrix} p_{k+1} \\ -q_{k+1} \end{bmatrix} e_k^T \right)$$

provided that $Bx_0 = 0$ and $q_0 = 0$, where T_k is the same as in Algorithm 1, and

$$P_k = [p_1 \quad \dots \quad p_k], \quad Q_k = [q_1 \quad \dots \quad q_k].$$

A consequence of Theorem 2 is that any CP-Krylov method is formally equivalent to the corresponding standard Krylov method applied to system (1) with preconditioner (2).

COROLLARY 1. *Let Algorithm 2 be initialized with $x_0 \in \mathbb{R}^n$ such that $Bx_0 = 0$, $q_0 = 0 \in \mathbb{R}^m$, and Algorithm 5 be initialized with the same x_0 and $y_0 \in \mathbb{R}^m$ such that (21) is satisfied. The k -th approximate solution of (1) computed by any Lanczos-based CP-Krylov method coincides with the k -th approximate solution obtained by formally applying the standard version of the same method to (1) with preconditioner (2).*

Although Corollary 1 states that standard Lanczos-based methods can be safely applied to (1) with preconditioner (2) and an appropriate starting point, Algorithm 2 reduces the computational effort by never requiring products with B or B^T . Only products with A and C are necessary. On the other hand, thanks to Theorem 2, specialized implementations of the standard Lanczos-based methods can be developed by exploiting the equalities $Bp_k + Cq_k = 0$ and $Bx_k - Cy_k = 0$, thus saving matrix-vector products. The computation involving s_{k+1} can be carried out, for example, as the update $q_{k-1} = q_k - \bar{z}_{k+1} - \beta_k q_{k-1}$ followed by $q_{k+1} = q_{k-1} - \alpha_k q_k$, or s_{k+1} can overwrite \bar{z}_{k+1} . Finally, once (2) has been factorized, storing B is no longer necessary, and this can be used to free memory if needed.

A consequence of Theorem 2 is a formal equivalence between the iterates generated by Lanczos-based methods applied by way of Algorithm 2 and Algorithm 5. This equivalence requires a re-interpretation of the optimality conditions associated with the Krylov method.

Consider, e.g., MINRES (Paige and Saunders, 1975). The residual associated with iterate $[x_k; w_k; y_k]$ generated by P-MINRES, with $w_k = -FE^T y_k$, is

$$r_{P,k} = \begin{bmatrix} r_{P,k,x} \\ r_{P,k,w} \\ r_{P,k,y} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} b \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} A & & B^T \\ & F^{-1} & E^T \\ B & E & \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_k \\ w_k \\ y_k \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} b - Ax_k - B^T y_k \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix},$$

315 where we used the fact that $Bx_k + Ew_k = 0$ for all k . This residual corresponds to
 316 the residual at iterate $[x_k; y_k]$ generated by CP-MINRES:

$$317 \quad r_{CP,k} = \begin{bmatrix} b \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} A & B^T \\ B & -C \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_k \\ y_k \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} b - Ax_k - B^T y_k \\ 0 \end{bmatrix},$$

318 where we exploited the fact that $Bx_k - Cy_k = 0$ for all k , which comes from $Bx_k +$
 319 $Ew_k = 0$ and $w_k = -FE^T y_k$.

320 We may apply the arguments of [Gould et al. \(2014, Section 3\)](#) to conclude that
 321 P-MINRES, and hence CP-MINRES, minimizes the deviation of $[r_{P,k,x}; 0]$ from the
 322 range space of N , i.e., as in (15),

$$323 \quad (23) \quad \|r_{P,k}\|_{[P]}^2 = (b - Ax_k - B^T y_k)^T h_k,$$

324 where

$$325 \quad \begin{bmatrix} G & & B^T \\ & F^{-1} & E^T \\ B & E & \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} h_k \\ f_k \\ l_k \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} b - Ax_k - B^T y_k \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

326 Because $h_k \in \text{Null}(B)$, we also have

$$327 \quad (24) \quad \|r_{P,k}\|_{[P]}^2 = (b - Ax_k)^T h_k.$$

328 Equivalently, h_k may be computed from

$$329 \quad \begin{bmatrix} G & B^T \\ B & -C \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} h_k \\ l_k \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} b - Ax_k \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

330 Because of its residual norm minimization property, CP-MINRES is appropriate
 331 to solve saddle-point systems in a linesearch inexact-Newton context, where we seek
 332 to reduce the residual of the Newton-like equations (1) in an appropriate space.

333 The same reasoning applies to the constraint-preconditioned version of any Lanczos-
 334 based Krylov method. For example, [Paige and Saunders \(1975\)](#) derive the conjugate
 335 gradient method of [Hestenes and Stiefel \(1952\)](#) directly from the Lanczos process. The
 336 nullspace variant of the constraint-preconditioned version, Lanczos CP-CG, generates
 337 iterates \hat{x}_k so as to minimize the energy norm of the error, i.e.,

$$338 \quad \|\hat{e}_k\|_{\widehat{M}}^2 = \hat{e}_k^T \widehat{M} \hat{e}_k,$$

339 where $\hat{e}_k = \hat{x}_k - \hat{x}_*$, and \hat{x}_* is the exact solution of (9). The definitions (10) yield

$$340 \quad \|\hat{e}_k\|_{\widehat{M}}^2 = (\hat{x}_k - \hat{x}_*)^T Z^T M Z (\hat{x}_k - \hat{x}_*) \\ 341 \quad = (x_k - x_*)^T A (x_k - x_*) + (w_k - w_*)^T F^{-1} (w_k - w^*) \\ 342 \quad = (x_k - x_*)^T A (x_k - x_*) + (y_k - y_*)^T C (y_k - y_*),$$

344 where we used again the relationship $w_k = -FE^T y_k$ between iterates of P-CG and
 345 CP-CG. For Lanczos CP-CG to be applicable, \widehat{M} must be positive definite, which
 346 occurs when the sum of the number of negative eigenvalues of K and C is m ([Dollar](#)
 347 [et al., 2006](#), Theorem 2.1).

348 We can derive a “traditional” CP-CG implementation by applying the usual
 349 transformations to the Lanczos CP-CG. The result coincides with the implementation

of Dollar et al. (2006), although the latter authors assume that B has full row rank for specific purposes. It is also equivalent to that of Cafieri, D'Apuzzo, De Simone, and di Serafino (2007a) for (1) with positive definite C . The above suggests that CP-CG is appropriate to solve saddle-point systems in constrained optimization where (1) is used to minimize a quadratic model of a penalty function and sufficient decrease of this quadratic model is sought, such as in trust-region methods.

Our last example considers SYMMLQ (Paige and Saunders, 1975), which does not require \widehat{M} to be positive definite but, like CG, requires (1) to be consistent. Its constraint-preconditioned version, CP-SYMMLQ, computes $[x_k; y_k]$ so as to minimize the error in a norm defined by the preconditioner, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} \widehat{e}_k^T \widehat{P}^{-1} \widehat{e}_k &= (\widehat{x}_k - \widehat{x}_*)^T (Z^T P Z)^{-1} (\widehat{x}_k - \widehat{x}_*) \\ &= (\widehat{x}_k - \widehat{x}_*)^T Z^T Z (Z^T P Z)^{-1} Z^T Z (\widehat{x}_k - \widehat{x}_*) \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} x_k - x_* \\ w_k - w_* \end{bmatrix}^T P_G \begin{bmatrix} x_k - x_* \\ w_k - w_* \end{bmatrix}. \end{aligned}$$

where we used similar identifications as above and assumed, without loss of generality, that Z has orthonormal columns. In other words, if we define

$$(25) \quad \begin{bmatrix} G & & B^T \\ & F^{-1} & E^T \\ B & & E \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} e_x \\ e_w \\ \bar{e} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_k - x_* \\ w_k - w_* \\ 0 \end{bmatrix},$$

then

$$\widehat{e}_k^T \widehat{P}^{-1} \widehat{e}_k = (x_k - x_*)^T e_x + (w_k - w_*)^T e_w = e_x^T G e_x + e_w^T F^{-1} e_w.$$

By (5) and (25), there exists a vector e_y such that $e_w = -F E^T e_y$, and thus $e_w^T F^{-1} e_w = e_y^T C e_y$. The second block row of (25) premultiplied by E yields $EF(w_k - w_*) - C\bar{e} = -C e_y$, so that (25) can be written as

$$\begin{bmatrix} G & B^T \\ B & -C \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} e_x \\ e_y \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_k - x_* \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Finally, CP-SYMMLQ minimizes

$$\widehat{e}_k^T \widehat{P}^{-1} \widehat{e}_k = e_x^T G e_x + e_y^T C e_y.$$

5. Constraint-Preconditioned Arnoldi Process and Associated Krylov Solvers. A constraint-preconditioned version of the Arnoldi process can be derived by reasoning as in Section 3, obtaining Algorithm 3. The equivalence between the projected version (Algorithm 6 in Appendix A) and the constraint-preconditioned version is stated in Theorem 3, which is akin to Theorem 1.

THEOREM 3. *Let E and F be as defined in (4) and G chosen to satisfy Assumption 2.1. Let $q_0 \in \mathbb{R}^m$ be arbitrary. Then, Algorithm 6 in Appendix A with starting guesses $x_0 \in \mathbb{R}^m$ and $w_0 = -F E^T q_0$, such that $B x_0 + E w_0 = 0$, is equivalent to Algorithm 3 with starting guesses x_0 and q_0 . In particular, for all k , the vectors $v_{k,x}$ and $v_{k,w}$ and the scalars $h_{i,k}$ in Algorithm 6 are equal to the vectors p_k and $F E^T q_k$, and to the scalars $h_{i,k}$ in Algorithm 3, respectively.*

As in the case of the Lanczos process, the CP-Arnoldi process is equivalent to applying the corresponding standard Arnoldi process to system (1) with preconditioner (2) (see Algorithm 7 in Appendix A), as stated in the next theorem.

Algorithm 3 Constraint-Preconditioned Arnoldi Process

```

1: choose  $[x_0; q_0]$  such that  $Bx_0 - Cq_0 = 0$  initial guess
2:  $p_0 = 0$  initial Arnoldi vector
3:  $u_0 = b - Ax_0, t_0 = Cq_0$ 
4:  $[\bar{p}_1; \bar{z}_1] \leftarrow$  solution of (17) with right-hand side  $[u_0; -t_0]$ 
5:  $p_1 = \bar{p}_1$ 
6:  $q_1 = q_0 - \bar{z}_1$ 
7:  $h_{1,0} = (p_1^T u_0 + q_1^T t_0)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ 
8: if  $h_{1,0} \neq 0$  then
9:    $p_1 = p_1/h_{1,0}, q_1 = q_1/h_{1,0}$ 
10: end if
11:  $k = 1$ 
12: while  $h_{k,k-1} \neq 0$  do
13:    $u_k = Ap_k, t_k = Cq_k$ 
14:    $[\bar{p}_{k+1}; \bar{z}_{k+1}] \leftarrow$  solution of (17) with right-hand side  $[u_k; -t_k]$ 
15:    $p_{k+1} = \bar{p}_{k+1}$ 
16:    $q_{k+1} = q_k - \bar{z}_{k+1}$ 
17:   for  $i = 1, \dots, k$  do
18:      $h_{i,k} = p_i^T u_k + q_i^T t_k$   $= p_i^T Ap_k + q_i^T Cq_k$ 
19:      $p_{k+1} = p_{k+1} - h_{i,k}p_i$ 
20:      $q_{k+1} = q_{k+1} - h_{i,k}q_i$ 
21:   end for
22:    $h_{k+1,k} = (p_{k+1}^T u_k + q_{k+1}^T t_k)^{\frac{1}{2}}$   $= (p_{k+1}^T Ap_k + q_{k+1}^T Cq_k)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ 
23:   if  $h_{k+1,k} \neq 0$  then
24:      $p_{k+1} = p_{k+1}/h_{k+1,k}, q_{k+1} = q_{k+1}/h_{k+1,k}$ 
25:   end if
26:    $k = k + 1$ 
27: end while

```

THEOREM 4. *Let Algorithm 3 be initialized with $x_0 \in \mathbb{R}^n$ such that $Bx_0 = 0$, $q_0 = 0 \in \mathbb{R}^m$, and Algorithm 7 be initialized with the same x_0 and $y_0 \in \mathbb{R}^m$ such that (21) is satisfied. Then, for all $k \geq 0$, $v_{k,x} = p_k$ and $v_{k,y} = -q_k$, where $[v_{k,x}; v_{k,y}]$ is the k -th Arnoldi vector generated in Algorithm 7, and p_k and q_k are the k -th Arnoldi vectors generated in Algorithm 3. In addition, the scalars $h_{i,k}$ computed at each iteration are the same in both algorithms.*

Theorem 4 allows us to develop a constraint-preconditioned variant of any Krylov method based on the Arnoldi process, using a starting guess satisfying (21). Such variants are equivalent to their standard counterparts preconditioned with (2), but are computationally cheaper, as in the case of Lanczos-based methods. Furthermore, CP-Krylov versions of optimal Arnoldi-based Krylov methods preserve the minimization properties of these methods in the sense explained in Section 4. For example, the constraint-preconditioned version of GMRES (Saad and Schultz, 1986) minimizes the norm of the deviation of the residual from $\text{Range}(N)$ similarly to MINRES. Below, we denote $\text{GMRES}(\ell)$ the variant of GMRES that is restarted every ℓ iterations.

Obtaining constraint-preconditioned versions of $\text{GMRES}(\ell)$ and DQGMRES is straightforward, by restarting and truncating the CP-Arnoldi basis generation process, respectively, as in the standard case (Saad, 2003). Note that DQGMRES with memory 2, i.e., with orthogonalization of each Arnoldi vector against the two previous

vectors only, is equivalent to CP-MINRES in exact arithmetic when A is symmetric. In finite precision arithmetic, DQGMRES with a larger memory may dampen the loss of orthogonality among the Lanczos vectors and act as a local reorthogonalization procedure, although we did not observe significant differences in [Section 7](#).

[Dollar \(2007, Theorems 4.1 and 4.3\)](#) establishes that if C is positive semi-definite of rank p , $P^{-1}K$ has an eigenvalue at 1 of multiplicity $2m - p$, while the remaining $n - m + p$ eigenvalues are defined by a generalized eigenvalue problem. A remark after ([Dollar, 2007, Theorem 4.1](#)) states that [Assumption 2.1](#) ensures that all eigenvalues are real. In addition, the dimension of the Krylov space is at most $\min(n - m + p + 2, n + m)$. Inspection reveals that [Dollar's](#) proofs of those results do not use the fact that A is symmetric; the results hold for general A . [Loghin \(2017\)](#) establishes similar results on the eigenvalues of non-regularized saddle-point matrices for general A and general G . Clustering eigenvalues accelerates convergence of nonsymmetric Krylov solvers in many practical cases, although the convergence behavior of such solvers is not fully characterized by the eigenvalues ([Greenbaum, Pták, and Strakoš, 1996](#)).

6. Implementation Issues. We implemented the constraint-preconditioned variants of the Lanczos-CG, MINRES, SYMMLQ, GMRES(ℓ) and DQGMRES methods for (1) in a MATLAB library named `cpkrylov`. For completeness, we also included in the library an implementation of the CP-CG method in the form given by [Dollar et al. \(2006\)](#). We think that `cpkrylov` can be useful as a basis for the development of more sophisticated numerical software.

All solvers are accessed via a common interface exposed by the main driver `reg_cpkrylov()`, which performs pre-processing operations, calls the requested solver, performs post-processing operations, and returns solutions and statistics to the user. `cpkrylov` is freely available from github.com/optimizers/cpkrylov.

Because A is never required as an explicit matrix, we allow the user to supply it as an abstract linear operator as implemented in the Spot linear operator toolbox². Spot allows us to use the familiar matrix notation with operators for which a representation as an explicit matrix is unavailable or inefficient. This affords the user flexibility in defining A while keeping the implementation of the various Krylov methods as readable as if A were a matrix.

[Gould et al. \(2001, 2014\)](#) observe that the numerical stability of projected Krylov solvers depends on keeping $[x_k; w_k]$ in $\text{Null}(N)$. While the iterates lie in the nullspace in exact arithmetic, $[x_k; w_k]$ may have a non-negligible component in $\text{Range}(N^T)$ because of roundoff error. In turn, the stability of CP-Krylov solvers depends on how accurately $[x_k; y_k]$ satisfies

$$Bx_k - Cy_k = 0.$$

[Gould et al. \(2001\)](#) suggest to increase the accuracy by applying iterative refinement after solving (17) with a direct method. In `cpkrylov`, the constraint preconditioner P is implemented as a Spot operator P such that writing $\mathbf{z} = P\mathbf{r}$, where $\mathbf{z} = [\mathbf{z}_1; \mathbf{z}_2]$ and $\mathbf{r} = [\mathbf{r}_1; \mathbf{r}_2]$, corresponds to solving

$$(26) \quad \begin{bmatrix} G & B^T \\ B & -C \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} z_1 \\ z_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} r_1 \\ r_2 \end{bmatrix},$$

and automatically performing iterative refinement if requested by the user or if the residual norm of (26) exceeds a given tolerance.

²www.cs.ubc.ca/labs/scl/spot

434 An alternative approach to minimizing the size of the component of $[x_k; w_k]$ in
 435 $\text{Range}(N^T)$ suggested by Gould et al. (2001) is to perform *iterative semi-refinement*.
 436 The latter consists in noting that the solution of (14) is not affected (in exact arithmetic)
 437 if we add a vector lying in $\text{Range}(N^T)$ to $[u_x; u_w]$ in the right-hand side. Such a
 438 vector is available cheaply in the form of $[B^T \bar{z}; E^T \bar{z}]$ where \bar{z} is the trailing segment
 439 of the solution of the most recent projection step (14), and $\bar{z} = 0$ at the first projection
 440 step. The net result is that instead of (17), we solve

$$(27) \quad \begin{bmatrix} G & B^T \\ B & -C \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \bar{p}_{k+1} \\ \bar{z}_{k+1} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} u_{k,x} - B^T \bar{z}_k \\ -(t_k - C \bar{z}_k) \end{bmatrix}, \quad \bar{z}_0 := 0.$$

442 By default, the matrix of (26) is factorized by way of MATLAB's `ldl()`. Spot
 443 allows us to separate the implementation of the preconditioner from that of other
 444 phases of solvers, so that future extensions to the former (e.g., the case where applying
 445 P results from a different factorization) will not require changes to the latter. Our
 446 implementation of P is transparent to the user, who must only pass the matrices G ,
 447 B and C to `reg_cpkrylov()`.

448 All CP-Krylov solvers stop when

$$(28) \quad \|r_{P,k}\|_{[P]} \leq \epsilon_a + \|r_{P,0}\|_{[P]} \epsilon_r,$$

449 where $\|r_{P,k}\|_{[P]}$ is defined in (23) (or, equivalently, in (24)), and ϵ_a and ϵ_r are tolerances
 450 given by the user (default values are also set in our implementations). Note that, for
 451 all the CP-Krylov solvers except CP-DQGMRES, $\|r_{P,k}\|_{[P]}$ is obtained as a byproduct
 452 of other computations performed in algorithm. CP-DQGMRES computes an estimate
 453 of the residual norm only. A computationally cheap overestimate of the residual norm
 454 could be used in the stopping criterion, but this may unnecessarily increase the number
 455 of iterations (Saad and Wu, 1996, Section 3.1). A maximum number of iterations can
 456 be also specified for all solvers.

457 So far, we have considered the case where the last m entries of the right-hand side
 458 of (1) are zero. When the right-hand side has the general form $[b_1; b_2]$ with $b_2 \neq 0$,
 459 we can compute Δx and Δy such that
 460

$$(29) \quad B\Delta x - C\Delta y = b_2,$$

461 by applying P to $[0; b_2]$, and subsequently solve (1) with $b = b_1 - A\Delta x - B^T \Delta y$. The
 462 solution of the original system is $[x + \Delta x; y + \Delta y]$. These pre- and post-processing
 463 steps are implemented in `reg_cpkrylov()`.
 464

465 **7. Numerical Experiments.** We report results obtained by applying some
 466 solvers from the `cpkrylov` library to regularized saddle-point systems arising in the
 467 application of the primal-dual interior point solver PDCO to convex quadratic pro-
 468 gramming problems (see web.stanford.edu/group/SOL/software/pdco/). PDCO
 469 solves linearly constrained optimization problems with a smooth convex objective
 470 function in the form

$$(30) \quad \begin{aligned} & \underset{x \in \mathbb{R}^n, r \in \mathbb{R}^m}{\text{minimize}} && f(x) + \frac{1}{2} \|D_1 x\|^2 + \frac{1}{2} \|r\|^2 \\ & \text{subject to} && Bx + D_2 r = c \\ & && l \leq x \leq u, \end{aligned}$$

472 where $f : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is smooth and convex, $B \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$, and D_1 and D_2 are positive-
 473 definite diagonal matrices that provide primal and dual regularization. In particular,

474 D_2 determines whether $Bx = c$ should be satisfied accurately or in the least-squares
 475 sense.

At each iteration of PDCO, a Newton step is applied to suitably perturbed KKT conditions associated with (30). The Newton step requires the solution of a linear system, which can be cast into the form (1) by a combination of permutation operations and/or inexpensive block eliminations. Possibly the most common saddle-point formulation is

$$K_2 = \begin{bmatrix} A & B^T \\ B & -C \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} H + D_1^2 + X_1^{-1}Z_1 + X_2^{-1}Z_2 & B^T \\ & B \\ & & -D_2^2 \end{bmatrix}$$

476 where H is the Hessian of the objective function at the current approximation of
 477 the optimal solution, $X_1 = \text{diag}(x_1)$, $X_2 = \text{diag}(x_2)$, $Z_1 = \text{diag}(z_1)$, $Z_2 = \text{diag}(z_2)$,
 478 $x_1 = x - l > 0$, $x_2 = u - x > 0$, and $z_1 > 0$ and $z_2 > 0$ are the corresponding dual
 479 variable estimates. In our experiments, H is constant because f is quadratic. More
 480 details are available from web.stanford.edu/group/SOL/software/pdco/pdco.pdf.

Recently, unreduced KKT systems have attracted the interest of researchers because of their better spectral properties, especially as the interior point iterates approach the solution of the optimization problem (Greif, Moulding, and Orban, 2014; Morini, Simoncini, and Tani, 2016). Other symmetric and unsymmetric saddle-point formulations are obtained with simple operations. In particular, within PDCO we used the unreduced symmetric saddle-point formulation

$$K_{3.5} = \begin{bmatrix} A & B^T \\ B & -C \end{bmatrix} = \left[\begin{array}{c|cc} H + D_1^2 & B^T & Z^{\frac{1}{2}} \\ \hline B & -D_2^2 & 0 \\ Z^{\frac{1}{2}} & 0 & -X \end{array} \right],$$

where $X = \text{diag}([x_1; x_2])$ and $Z = \text{diag}([z_1; z_2])$. We also considered the unsymmetric saddle-point formulation

$$K_{3p} = \begin{bmatrix} A & B^T \\ B & -C \end{bmatrix} = \left[\begin{array}{cc|c} H + D_1^2 & I & B^T \\ \hline -Z & X & 0 \\ B & 0 & -D_2^2 \end{array} \right],$$

481 which has the same structure as the saddle-point matrix in equation (2.5a) of (Greif
 482 et al., 2014) up to a permutation.

483 For all the saddle-point formulations, the constraint preconditioner P in (2) was
 484 defined by choosing G equal to the diagonal of the leading block A . This is a common
 485 choice in interior point methods—see, e.g., (D’Apuzzo et al., 2010). In our experiments,
 486 iterative refinement never needed to be performed.

The CP-Krylov solvers were stopped using an adaptive criterion that relates the accuracy in the solution of the KKT linear system to the duality measure at the current interior point iteration, as suggested by Cafieri, D’Apuzzo, De Simone, and di Serafino (2007b). Thus, criterion (28) was applied by setting $\epsilon_r = 0$ and

$$\epsilon_a = \max \left\{ \min \left\{ 10^{-2}\mu, 10^{-2} \right\}, 10^{-6} \right\},$$

487 where μ is the the barrier parameter in PDCO.

488 We run PDCO on the CUTEst (Gould, Orban, and Toint, 2015) problems reported
 489 in Table 1. We use the models translated³ into the AMPL modeling language (Fourer,

³github.com/mpf/Optimization-Test-Problems

Problem	K_2 size	$K_{3.5}$ (K_{3p}) size
cvxqp1_s	200	400
cvxqp1_m	2000	4000
cvxqp1_l	20000	40000
cvxqp2_s	150	350
cvxqp2_m	1500	3500
cvxqp2_l	15000	35000
cvxqp3_s	250	450
cvxqp3_m	2500	4500
cvxqp3_l	25000	45000
gouldqp3	1397	2795
gouldqp2	1397	2795
mosarqp1	3900	7100
mosarqp2	3900	3600
stcqp1	8201	16395
stcqp2	8201	16395

TABLE 1

CUTEst problems used in the experiments.

490 [Gay, and Kernighan, 2002](#)). Our version of PDCO has been modified to take an
 491 optimization problem in the form of an instance of the `nlmodel` class as argument,
 492 which is defined in the `model` Matlab package.⁴ The `amplmodel` subclass of `nlmodel`
 493 reads an AMPL `n1` file by way of the `AmplMEXInterface` package⁵ and conforms to
 494 the `model` interface expected by our version of PDCO. The rest of PDCO is identical
 495 to the original version. For the problem received by PDCO to have the form (30), it
 496 is necessary to introduce slack variables. In our implementation, linear inequalities
 497 $\ell \leq Ax \leq u$ are transformed to $Ax - s = 0$ and $\ell \leq s \leq u$. The transformation is
 498 performed by the `slackmodel` class, which receives an arbitrary instance of `nlmodel`,
 499 including arbitrary instances of `amplmodel`, and adds slack variables as just described.
 500 The options passed to PDCO, including scaling parameters, are the same as those
 501 described by [Orban \(2015\)](#).

502 The problems are chosen so that H is non-diagonal; otherwise, for K_2 and $K_{3.5}$
 503 the constraint preconditioner would be equal to the saddle-point matrix. The table
 504 also shows the sizes of K_2 and $K_{3.5}$ (or K_{3p}).

505 We ran PDCO with the saddle-point matrices K_2 and $K_{3.5}$, using CP-CG,
 506 CP-MINRES, CP-DQGMRES(ℓ) and CP-GMRES(ℓ) as Krylov solvers. By CP-
 507 DQGMRES(ℓ) we denote CP-DQGMRES with memory parameter ℓ , i.e., the number
 508 of Arnoldi vectors to be stored in the truncated CP-Arnoldi process. We set $\ell = 2$; in
 509 this case CP-DQGMRES is equivalent to CP-MINRES in exact arithmetic. We also
 510 ran PDCO with K_{3p} using CP-DQGMRES(ℓ) and CP-GMRES(ℓ) with various values
 511 of ℓ . The goal of the experiments is to illustrate the behavior of CP-Krylov solvers
 512 inside an interior-point method.

513 PDCO was run on a 2.5 GHz Intel Core i7 processor with 16 GB of RAM,
 514 4 MB of L3 cache and the macOS 10.13.6 operating system, using MATLAB R2018b.
 515 Execution times were measured in seconds, by using the MATLAB function `timeit`,
 516 which removes some of the noise inherent to time measurements by calling a specified
 517 function multiple times and returning the median of the measurements.

518 [Tables 2 to 5](#) summarize the results obtained with K_2 and $K_{3.5}$ using CP-CG and
 519 CP-MINRES. For each problem, the number of PDCO and CP-Krylov iterations is
 520 reported, as well as the time for running PDCO, and the total time for building the
 521 constraint preconditioner and for solving the linear systems. We see that CP-MINRES

⁴github.com/optimizers/model

⁵github.com/optimizers/AmplMexInterface

name	outer it	inner it	PDCO time	prec time	solve time
cvxqp1_s	17	80	8.343e-02	2.741e-02	2.034e-02
cvxqp1_m	19	103	4.110e-01	6.130e-02	1.394e-01
cvxqp1_l	20	138	1.632e+01	3.444e-01	6.159e-01
cvxqp2_s	17	80	6.298e-02	2.587e-02	1.657e-02
cvxqp2_m	19	118	2.785e-01	3.657e-02	1.222e-01
cvxqp2_l	20	140	8.224e+00	1.149e-01	5.656e-01
cvxqp3_s	20	72	8.252e-02	3.347e-02	2.051e-02
cvxqp3_m	19	99	5.639e-01	9.184e-02	1.791e-01
cvxqp3_l	20	137	2.409e+01	5.460e-01	2.602e-01
gouldqp3	10	19	8.684e-02	2.001e-02	2.358e-02
gouldqp2	9	12	6.888e-02	1.802e-02	2.059e-02
mosarqp1	17	54	2.494e-01	8.799e-02	1.394e-01
mosarqp2	16	73	1.785e-01	6.224e-02	9.700e-02
stcqp1	15	99	7.984e+00	3.666e+00	8.459e-01
stcqp2	15	161	4.205e+00	6.892e-02	8.434e-01

TABLE 2
Results for K_2 with solver CP-CG. Times are in seconds.

name	outer it	inner it	PDCO time	prec time	solve time
cvxqp1_s	17	80	7.263e-02	2.767e-02	1.941e-02
cvxqp1_m	19	103	4.348e-01	6.010e-02	1.419e-01
cvxqp1_l	20	137	1.671e+01	3.416e-01	6.078e-01
cvxqp2_s	17	80	6.584e-02	2.909e-02	1.832e-02
cvxqp2_m	19	118	2.927e-01	3.725e-02	1.207e-01
cvxqp2_l	20	140	8.488e+00	1.182e-01	5.661e-01
cvxqp3_s	20	72	8.809e-02	3.386e-02	2.037e-02
cvxqp3_m	19	99	5.899e-01	9.515e-02	1.770e-01
cvxqp3_l	20	136	2.524e+01	5.459e-01	2.649e-01
gouldqp3	10	19	8.986e-02	2.029e-02	2.283e-02
gouldqp2	9	12	7.338e-02	1.892e-02	2.567e-02
mosarqp1	17	54	2.587e-01	8.396e-02	1.429e-01
mosarqp2	16	73	1.944e-01	6.443e-02	9.866e-02
stcqp1	15	99	8.114e+00	3.693e+00	8.441e-01
stcqp2	15	158	4.349e+00	6.995e-02	8.349e-01

TABLE 3
Results for K_2 with solver CP-MINRES. Times are in seconds.

522 performs a slightly smaller number of iterations than CP-CG on some problems, which
523 may be beneficial if very large systems are solved. CP-MINRES is adequate in the
524 context of a linesearch inexact Newton method such as PDCO because it reduces
525 the residual norm monotonically by design. Fong and Saunders (2012) observe that
526 MINRES possesses other desirable properties that are generally attributed to CG.

527 We also observe that the number of CP-Krylov iterations with $K_{3.5}$ is always
528 smaller than with K_2 , which may be due to the smaller condition number of $K_{3.5}$
529 (Greif et al., 2014; Morini et al., 2016). On cvxqp3_s, $K_{3.5}$ also results in a smaller
530 number of PDCO iterations. We used the MATLAB function `condest` to estimate the
531 condition numbers of K_2 and $K_{3.5}$ encountered during the PDCO iterations for each
532 problem. On the cvxqp problems, the largest value of `condest`($K_{3.5}$) is between three
533 and four orders of magnitude smaller than the largest value of `condest`(K_2). The
534 factor is between five and seven orders of magnitude on the gouldqp problems, one to
535 two orders on the mosarqp problems, and two to three orders on the stcqp problems.
536 While such measurements do not tell the whole story and it would be more accurate to
537 measure the condition number of (10), they tend to confirm that the condition number
538 of $K_{3.5}$ is provably bounded if strict complementarity is satisfied. However, by looking
539 at the times for PDCO we see that there is no clear winner between K_2 and $K_{3.5}$.

540 We do not show the details for CP-DQGMRES(2) and CP-GMRES(2), because
541 they do not add much to the discussion. We summarize the results as follows: CP-

name	outer it	inner it	PDCO time	prec time	solve time
cvxqp1_s	17	66	7.679e-02	2.934e-02	2.641e-02
cvxqp1_m	19	86	5.525e-01	8.451e-02	2.525e-01
cvxqp1_l	20	120	1.822e+01	9.360e-01	1.873e+00
cvxqp2_s	17	64	6.106e-02	2.709e-02	1.397e-02
cvxqp2_m	19	101	3.352e-01	4.918e-02	1.557e-01
cvxqp2_l	20	123	9.482e+00	3.256e-01	1.527e+00
cvxqp3_s	18	50	7.976e-02	3.220e-02	2.473e-02
cvxqp3_m	19	81	7.392e-01	1.396e-01	2.796e-01
cvxqp3_l	20	119	2.747e+01	1.704e+00	1.956e+00
gouldqp3	10	11	5.951e-01	4.850e-01	4.546e-02
gouldqp2	9	6	9.142e-02	3.187e-02	3.008e-02
mosarqp1	17	39	4.348e-01	1.576e-01	2.426e-01
mosarqp2	16	60	3.302e-01	1.226e-01	1.681e-01
stcqp1	15	86	9.063e+00	4.473e+00	1.212e+00
stcqp2	15	147	3.744e+00	1.356e-01	2.108e-01

TABLE 4
Results for $K_{3.5}$ with solver CP-CG. Times are in seconds.

name	outer it	inner it	PDCO time	prec time	solve time
cvxqp1_s	17	65	8.132e-02	2.884e-02	2.627e-02
cvxqp1_m	19	86	5.690e-01	8.101e-02	2.570e-01
cvxqp1_l	20	119	1.889e+01	9.442e-01	1.885e+00
cvxqp2_s	17	64	6.271e-02	3.008e-02	1.430e-02
cvxqp2_m	19	101	3.437e-01	4.962e-02	1.581e-01
cvxqp2_l	20	123	9.828e+00	3.272e-01	1.560e+00
cvxqp3_s	18	50	8.203e-02	3.222e-02	2.488e-02
cvxqp3_m	19	81	7.426e-01	1.360e-01	2.825e-01
cvxqp3_l	20	118	2.808e+01	1.758e+00	1.961e+00
gouldqp3	10	11	5.528e-01	4.802e-01	4.551e-02
gouldqp2	9	6	9.202e-02	3.106e-02	3.056e-02
mosarqp1	17	39	4.640e-01	1.594e-01	2.458e-01
mosarqp2	16	60	3.276e-01	1.247e-01	1.738e-01
stcqp1	15	85	9.073e+00	4.458e+00	1.197e+00
stcqp2	15	144	3.777e+00	1.354e-01	2.059e-01

TABLE 5
Results for $K_{3.5}$ with solver CP-MINRES. Times are in seconds.

542 DQGMRES(2) results in the same number of PDCO and CP-Krylov iterations as
543 CP-MINRES, as expected, and the corresponding times are comparable with those of
544 MINRES. CP-GMRES(2) results in an increase in the number of CP-Krylov iterations
545 as compared with MINRES. Whereas CP-DQGMRES with $\ell > 2$ may be viewed as
546 CP-MINRES with a form of partial reorthogonalization, setting $\ell = 4$ did not yield
547 any improvement on the symmetric formulations.

548 The results with CP-DQGMRES(ℓ) and CP-GMRES(ℓ) on K_{3p} are not favorable.
549 In general, the unsymmetric CP-Krylov solvers on K_{3p} are much less efficient than the
550 symmetric ones on K_2 and $K_{3.5}$. For example, with $\ell = 500$ the number of CPKrylov
551 iterations is much larger than in the symmetric case and there are some problems where
552 CP-DQGMRES(ℓ) and CP-GMRES(ℓ) cannot always satisfy the stopping criterion.
553 In these cases, they halt because a maximum number of CP-Krylov iterations equal
554 to $2n$ is achieved, thus preventing PDCO from computing the optimal solution by
555 its maximum number of iterations, which is set as $\min\{\max\{30, n\}, 50\}$. Among the
556 possible reasons, we mention the non-normality of K_{3p} and the choice of the $(1, 1)$
557 block G of the preconditioner. A similar behavior has been observed by using the
558 MATLAB function `gmres` with the constraint preconditioner. A more efficient choice
559 of G and a better formulation than K_{3p} are the subject of further investigation.

560 We ran all our tests a second time with iterative semi-refinement (27) activated,
561 but did not observe any difference in the number of inner or outer iterations.

8. Discussion. We extended the approach of Gould et al. (2014) to saddle-point systems with regularization and provided principles from which to derive constrained-preconditioned iterative methods. The resulting methods are conceptually equivalent to standard iterative methods applied to a reduced system in a way that preserves their properties, including quantities that increase or decrease monotonically at each iteration. Specifically, we discussed constraint-preconditioned versions of the CG-Lanczos, MINRES, SYMMLQ, GMRES(ℓ) and DQGMRES(ℓ) methods, and showed that they preserve the properties of the corresponding standard methods in a suitable reduced Krylov space. We illustrated our approach on methods based on the Lanczos and Arnoldi processes, but it applies equally to other processes, including those of Golub and Kahan (1965), Saunders, Simon, and Yip (1988), and the unsymmetric Lanczos (1952) bi-orthogonalization process. We implemented our constraint-preconditioned methods in a MATLAB library named `cpkrylov` that provides a basis for the development of more sophisticated numerical software.

An open question related to constraint preconditioners concerns the best way to reduce their computational cost. Inexact constraint preconditioners have been developed and analyzed, based on approximations of the Schur complement of the leading block of the constraint preconditioner or on other approximations (Lukšan and Vlček, 1998; Perugia and Simoncini, 2000; Durazzi and Ruggiero, 2003; Bergamaschi, Gondzio, Venturin, and Zilli, 2007; Sesana and Simoncini, 2013). Preconditioner updating techniques, producing inexact and exact constraint preconditioners, have been also proposed in order to reduce the cost of solving sequences of saddle-point systems (Bellavia, De Simone, di Serafino, and Morini, 2015, 2016; Fisher, Gratton, Gürol, Trémolet, and Vasseur, 2016; Bergamaschi, De Simone, di Serafino, and Martínez, 2018). It must be noted, however, that the inexact constraint preconditioners considered so far generally do not produce preconditioned vectors lying in the nullspace of the matrix N defined in (7), which is a key issue to obtain CP-preconditioned methods for (1) equivalent to suitably preconditioned Krylov methods for (9). On the other hand, inexact preconditioners have proven effective in reducing the computational time for the solution of large-scale saddle-point systems. A further possibility for lowering the cost of constraint preconditioners is to apply them inexactly using an iterative method. Of course, preserving the property of obtaining preconditioned vectors lying in the nullspace of N is a major issue. To the best of our knowledge, this approach has not been yet addressed in the literature.

Finally, it is worth investigating the choice of the (1, 1) block of the constraint preconditioner when solving non-normal saddle-point systems.

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References.

- W. E. Arnoldi. The principle of minimized iterations in the solution of the matrix eigenvalue problem. *Q. Appl. Math.*, 9:17–29, 1951. DOI: [10.1090/qam/42792](https://doi.org/10.1090/qam/42792).
- S. Bellavia, V. De Simone, D. di Serafino, and B. Morini. Updating constraint preconditioners for KKT systems in quadratic programming via low-rank corrections. *SIAM J. Optim.*, 25(3):1787–1808, 2015. DOI: [10.1137/130947155](https://doi.org/10.1137/130947155).
- S. Bellavia, V. De Simone, D. di Serafino, and B. Morini. On the update of constraint preconditioners for regularized KKT systems. *Comput. Optim. Appl.*, 65(2):339–360, 2016. DOI: [10.1007/s10589-016-9830-4](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10589-016-9830-4).
- M. Benzi, G. H. Golub, and J. Liesen. Numerical solution of saddle point problems. *Acta Numer.*, 14:1–137, 2005. DOI: [10.1017/S0962492904000212](https://doi.org/10.1017/S0962492904000212).
- L. Bergamaschi, J. Gondzio, M. Venturin, and G. Zilli. Inexact constraint preconditioners for

- 612 linear systems arising in interior point methods. *Comput. Optim. Appl.*, 36(2–3):137–147,
613 2007. DOI: [10.1007/s10589-006-9001-0](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10589-006-9001-0).
- 614 L. Bergamaschi, V. De Simone, D. di Serafino, and A. Martínez. BFGS-like updates of
615 constraint preconditioners for sequences of KKT linear systems in quadratic programming.
616 *Numer. Linear Algebra Appl.*, 25(5):e2144, 2018. DOI: [10.1002/nla.2144](https://doi.org/10.1002/nla.2144).
- 617 C. Brezinski and M. Redivo-Zaglia. Transpose-free Lanczos-type algorithms for nonsymmetric
618 linear systems. *Numer. Algor.*, 17(1–2):67–103, 1998. DOI: [10.1023/A:1012085428800](https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1012085428800).
- 619 S. Cafieri, M. D’Apuzzo, V. De Simone, and D. di Serafino. On the iterative solution of KKT
620 systems in potential reduction software for large-scale quadratic problems. *Comput. Optim.*
621 *Appl.*, 38(1):27–45, 2007a. DOI: [10.1007/s10589-007-9035-y](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10589-007-9035-y).
- 622 S. Cafieri, M. D’Apuzzo, V. De Simone, and D. di Serafino. Stopping criteria for inner
623 iterations in inexact potential reduction methods: a computational study. *Comput. Optim.*
624 *Appl.*, 36(2–3):165–193, 2007b. DOI: [10.1007/s10589-006-9007-7](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10589-006-9007-7).
- 625 T. F. Chan, L. de Pillis, and H. van der Vorst. Transpose-free formulations of Lanczos-type
626 methods for nonsymmetric linear systems. *Numer. Algor.*, 17(1–2):51–66, 1998. DOI:
627 [10.1023/A:1011637511962](https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1011637511962).
- 628 M. D’Apuzzo, V. De Simone, and D. di Serafino. On mutual impact of numerical linear
629 algebra and large-scale optimization with focus on interior point methods. *Comput. Optim.*
630 *Appl.*, 45(2):283–310, 2010. DOI: [10.1007/s10589-008-9226-1](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10589-008-9226-1).
- 631 V. De Simone, D. di Serafino, and B. Morini. On preconditioner updates for sequences of
632 saddle-point linear systems. *Communications in Applied and Industrial Mathematics*, 9(1):
633 35–41, 2018. DOI: [10.1515/caim-2018-0003](https://doi.org/10.1515/caim-2018-0003).
- 634 H. S. Dollar. Constraint-style preconditioners for regularized saddle point problems. *SIAM J.*
635 *Matrix Anal. Appl.*, 29(2):672–684, 2007. DOI: [10.1137/050626168](https://doi.org/10.1137/050626168).
- 636 H. S. Dollar, N. I. M. Gould, W. H. A. Schilders, and A. J. Wathen. Implicit-factorization
637 preconditioning and iterative solvers for regularized saddle-point systems. *SIAM J. Matrix*
638 *Anal. Appl.*, 28(1):170–189, 2006. DOI: [10.1137/05063427X](https://doi.org/10.1137/05063427X).
- 639 I. S. Duff. MA57—a code for the solution of sparse symmetric definite and indefinite systems.
640 *ACM Trans. Math. Software*, 30(2):118–144, 2004. DOI: [10.1145/992200.992202](https://doi.org/10.1145/992200.992202).
- 641 C. Durazzi and V. Ruggiero. Indefinitely preconditioned conjugate gradient method for large
642 sparse equality and inequality constrained quadratic problems. *Numer. Linear Algebra*
643 *Appl.*, 10(8):673–688, 2003. DOI: [10.1002/nla.308](https://doi.org/10.1002/nla.308).
- 644 M. Fisher, S. Gratton, S. Gürol, Y. Trémolet, and X. Vasseur. Low rank updates in
645 preconditioning the saddle point systems arising from data assimilation problems. *Optim.*
646 *Method Softw.*, 33(1):45–69, 2016. DOI: [10.1080/10556788.2016.1264398](https://doi.org/10.1080/10556788.2016.1264398).
- 647 D. C.-L. Fong and M. A. Saunders. CG versus MINRES: An empirical comparison. *SQU*
648 *Journal for Science*, 17(1):44–62, 2012.
- 649 R. Fourer, D. M. Gay, and B. W. Kernighan. *AMPL: A Modeling Language for Mathematical*
650 *Programming*. Duxbury Press / Brooks/Cole Publishing Company, 2002.
- 651 M. P. Friedlander and D. Orban. A primal-dual regularized interior-point method for convex
652 quadratic problems. *Math. Program. Comp.*, 4(1):71–107, 2012. DOI: [10.1007/s12532-012-0035-2](https://doi.org/10.1007/s12532-012-0035-2).
- 653 G. H. Golub and W. Kahan. Calculating the singular values and pseudo-inverse of a matrix.
654 *SIAM J. Numer. Anal.*, 2(2):205–224, 1965. DOI: [10.1137/0702016](https://doi.org/10.1137/0702016).
- 655 N. Gould, D. Orban, and Ph. Toint. CUTEst: a constrained and unconstrained testing
656 environment with safe threads for mathematical optimization. *Comput. Optim. Appl.*, 60
657 (3):545–557, 2015. DOI: [10.1007/s1058](https://doi.org/10.1007/s1058).
- 658 N. I. M. Gould, M. E. Hribar, and J. Nocedal. On the solution of equality constrained
659 quadratic problems arising in optimization. *SIAM J. Sci. Comput.*, 23(4):1375–1394, 2001.
660 DOI: [10.1137/S1064827598345667](https://doi.org/10.1137/S1064827598345667).
- 661 N. I. M. Gould, D. Orban, and T. Rees. Projected Krylov methods for saddle-point systems.
662 *SIAM J. Matrix Anal. Appl.*, 35(4):1329–1343, 2014. DOI: [10.1137/130916394](https://doi.org/10.1137/130916394).
- 663 A. Greenbaum, V. Pták, and Z. Strakoš. Any nonincreasing convergence curve is
664 possible for GMRES. *SIAM J. Matrix Anal. Appl.*, 17(3):465–469, 1996. DOI:
665

- 666 [10.1137/S0895479894275030](https://doi.org/10.1137/S0895479894275030).
- 667 C. Greif, E. Moulding, and D. Orban. Bounds on eigenvalues of matrices arising from
668 interior-point methods. *SIAM J. Optim.*, 24(1):49–83, 2014. DOI: [10.1137/120890600](https://doi.org/10.1137/120890600).
- 669 M. R. Hestenes and E. Stiefel. Methods of conjugate gradients for solving linear systems. *J.*
670 *Res. Natl. Bur. Stand.*, 49(6):409–436, 1952. DOI: [10.6028/jres.049.044](https://doi.org/10.6028/jres.049.044).
- 671 C. Lanczos. An iteration method for the solution of the eigenvalue problem of linear differential
672 and integral operators. *J. Res. Natl. Bur. Stand.*, 45:225–280, 1950.
- 673 C. Lanczos. Solution of systems of linear equations by minimized iterations. *J. Res. Natl.*
674 *Bur. Stand.*, 49(1):33–53, 1952. DOI: [10.6028/jres.049.006](https://doi.org/10.6028/jres.049.006).
- 675 D. Loghin. A note on constraint preconditioning. *SIAM J. Matrix Anal. Appl.*, 38(4):
676 1486–1495, 2017. DOI: [10.1137/16M1072036](https://doi.org/10.1137/16M1072036).
- 677 L. Lukšan and J. Vlček. Indefinitely preconditioned inexact Newton method for large sparse
678 equality constrained nonlinear programming problems. *Numer. Linear Algebra Appl.*, 5:219–
679 247, 1998. DOI: [10.1002/\(SICI\)1099-1506\(199805/06\)5:3<219::AID-NLA134>3.0.CO;2-7](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1099-1506(199805/06)5:3<219::AID-NLA134>3.0.CO;2-7).
- 680 B. Morini, V. Simoncini, and M. Tani. Spectral estimates for unreduced symmetric KKT
681 systems arising from interior point methods. *Numer. Linear Algebra Appl.*, 23:776–800,
682 2016. DOI: [10.1002/nla.2054](https://doi.org/10.1002/nla.2054).
- 683 D. Orban. Limited-memory LDL^T factorization of symmetric quasi-definite matrices with appli-
684 cation to constrained optimization. *Numer. Algor.*, 70(1):9–41, 2015. DOI: [10.1007/s11075-014-9933-x](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11075-014-9933-x).
- 685 C. C. Paige and M. A. Saunders. Solution of sparse indefinite systems of linear equations.
686 *SIAM J. Numer. Anal.*, 12(4):617–629, 1975. DOI: [10.1137/0712047](https://doi.org/10.1137/0712047).
- 687 I. Perugia and V. Simoncini. Block-diagonal and indefinite symmetric preconditioners for
688 mixed finite element formulations. *Numer. Linear Algebra Appl.*, 7(7–8):585–616, 2000.
689 DOI: [10.1002/1099-1506\(200010/12\)7:7/8<585::AID-NLA214>3.0.CO;2-F](https://doi.org/10.1002/1099-1506(200010/12)7:7/8<585::AID-NLA214>3.0.CO;2-F).
- 690 J. Pestana and A. J. Wathen. Natural preconditioning and iterative methods for saddle point
691 systems. *SIAM Review*, 57(1):51–71, 2015. DOI: [10.1137/130934921](https://doi.org/10.1137/130934921).
- 692 Y. Saad. *Iterative methods for sparse linear systems*. Society for Industrial and Applied
693 Mathematics, Philadelphia, PA, second edition, 2003. DOI: [10.1137/1.9780898718003](https://doi.org/10.1137/1.9780898718003).
- 694 Y. Saad and M. H. Schultz. GMRES: A generalized minimal residual algorithm for solving
695 nonsymmetric linear systems. *SIAM J. Sci. and Statist. Comput.*, 7(3):856–869, 1986. DOI:
696 [10.1137/0907058](https://doi.org/10.1137/0907058).
- 697 Y. Saad and K. Wu. DQGMRES: a direct quasi-minimal residual algorithm based on
698 incomplete orthogonalization. *Numer. Linear Algebra Appl.*, 3(4):329–343, 1996. DOI:
699 [10/fwxn2n](https://doi.org/10/fwxn2n).
- 700 M. A. Saunders, H. D. Simon, and E. L. Yip. Two conjugate-gradient-type methods
701 for unsymmetric linear equations. *SIAM J. Numer. Anal.*, 25(4):927–940, 1988. DOI:
702 [10.1137/0725052](https://doi.org/10.1137/0725052).
- 703 D. Sesana and V. Simoncini. Spectral analysis of inexact constraint preconditioning for
704 symmetric saddle point matrices. *Linear Algebra and its Applications*, 438(6):2683–2700,
705 2013. DOI: [10.1016/j.laa.2012.11.022](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.laa.2012.11.022).
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Appendix A. Standard Lanczos and Arnoldi Processes. For reference we state the preconditioned Lanczos process and the full-space Lanczos process for (1) with preconditioner (2). We also state the projected and full-space Arnoldi processes.

Algorithm 4 Lanczos Process for $Ax = b$ with Preconditioner $J = J^T > 0$

```

1: choose  $x_0$ 
2:  $v_0 = 0$ 
3:  $r_0 = b - Ax_0$ 
4: solve  $Jv_1 = r_0$ 
5:  $\beta_1 = (v_1^T r_0)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ 
6: if  $\beta_1 \neq 0$  then
7:    $v_1 = v_1/\beta_1$   $\|v_1\|_J = 1$ 
8: end if
9:  $k = 1$ 
10: while  $\beta_k \neq 0$  do
11:    $u_k = Av_k$ 
12:    $\alpha_k = u_k^T v_k$ 
13:   solve  $Jv_{k+1} = u_k$ 
14:    $v_{k+1} = v_{k+1} - \alpha_k v_k - \beta_k v_{k-1}$ 
15:    $\beta_{k+1} = (v_{k+1}^T u_k)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ 
16:   if  $\beta_{k+1} \neq 0$  then
17:      $v_{k+1} = v_{k+1}/\beta_k$   $\|v_{k+1}\|_J = 1$ 
18:   end if
19:    $k = k + 1$ 
20: end while

```

Algorithm 5 Full-Space Lanczos Process for (1) with Preconditioner (2)

1: choose $[x_0; y_0]$ such that $Bx_0 - Cy_0 = 0$

2: initialize

$$\begin{bmatrix} v_{0,x} \\ v_{0,y} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

3: set

$$Bx_0 - Cy_0 = 0 \Rightarrow r_{0,y} = 0$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} r_{0,x} \\ r_{0,y} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} b \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} A & B^T \\ B & -C \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_0 \\ y_0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} b - Ax_0 - B^T y_0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

4: obtain v_1 as the solution of

$$\begin{bmatrix} G & B^T \\ B & -C \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_{1,x} \\ v_{1,y} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} r_{0,x} \\ r_{0,y} \end{bmatrix}$$

5: $\beta_1 = (v_1^T r_0)^{\frac{1}{2}} = (v_{1,x}^T r_{0,x})^{\frac{1}{2}}$

6: **if** $\beta_1 \neq 0$ **then**

7: $v_1 = v_1/\beta_1$

8: **end if**

9: $k = 1$

10: **while** $\beta_k \neq 0$ **do**

11: compute

$$\begin{bmatrix} u_{k,x} \\ u_{k,y} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A & B^T \\ B & -C \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_{k,x} \\ v_{k,y} \end{bmatrix}$$

12: $\alpha_k = u_k^T v_k = v_{k,x}^T A v_{k,x} + 2v_{k,x}^T B^T v_{k,y} - v_{k,y}^T C v_{k,y}$

13: obtain v_{k+1} as the solution of

$$\begin{bmatrix} G & B^T \\ B & -C \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_{k+1,x} \\ v_{k+1,y} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} u_{k,x} \\ u_{k,y} \end{bmatrix}$$

14: $v_{k+1} = v_{k+1} - \alpha_k v_k - \beta_k v_{k-1}$

15: $\beta_{k+1} = (v_{k+1}^T u_k)^{\frac{1}{2}} = (v_{k+1,x}^T u_{k,x} + v_{k+1,y}^T u_{k,y})^{\frac{1}{2}}$

16: **if** $\beta_{k+1} \neq 0$ **then**

17: $v_{k+1} = v_{k+1}/\beta_{k+1}$

18: **end if**

19: $k = k + 1$

20: **end while**

Algorithm 6 Projected Arnoldi Process

```

1: choose  $[x_0; w_0]$  such that  $Bx_0 + Ew_0 = 0$ 
2:  $v_{0,x} = 0, v_{0,w} = -w_0$ 
3:  $u_{0,x} = b - Ax_0, u_{0,w} = -F^{-1}w_0$ 
4:  $[\bar{u}_{1,x}; \bar{u}_{1,w}; \bar{z}_1] \leftarrow$  solution of (14) with right-hand side  $[u_{0,x}; u_{0,w}; 0]$ 
5:  $v_{1,x} = \bar{u}_{1,x}, v_{1,w} = \bar{u}_{1,w}$   $v_1 = P_G u_0$ 
6:  $h_{1,0} = (v_{1,x}^T u_{0,x} + v_{1,w}^T u_{0,w})^{\frac{1}{2}}$ 
7: if  $h_{1,0} \neq 0$  then
8:    $v_{1,x} = v_{1,x}/h_{1,0}, v_{1,w} = v_{1,w}/h_{1,0}$ 
9: end if
10:  $k = 1$ 
11: while  $h_{k,k-1} \neq 0$  do
12:    $u_{k,x} = Av_{k,x}, u_{k,w} = F^{-1}v_{k,w}$ 
13:    $[\bar{u}_{k+1,x}; \bar{u}_{k+1,w}; \bar{z}_{k+1}] \leftarrow$  solution of (14) with right-hand side  $[u_{k,x}; u_{k,w}; 0]$ 
14:    $v_{k+1,x} = \bar{u}_{k+1,x}, v_{k+1,w} = \bar{u}_{k+1,w}$   $v_{k+1} = P_G u_k$ 
15:   for  $i = 1, \dots, k$  do
16:      $h_{i,k} = v_{i,x}^T u_{k,x} + v_{i,w}^T u_{k,w}$ 
17:      $v_{k+1,x} = v_{k+1,x} - h_{i,k}v_{i,x}, v_{k+1,w} = v_{k+1,w} - h_{i,k}v_{i,w}$ 
18:   end for
19:    $h_{k+1,k} = (v_{k+1,x}^T u_{k,x} + v_{k+1,w}^T u_{k,w})^{\frac{1}{2}}$ 
20:   if  $h_{k+1,k} \neq 0$  then
21:      $v_{k+1,x} = v_{k+1,x}/h_{k+1,k}, v_{k+1,w} = v_{k+1,w}/h_{k+1,k}$ 
22:   end if
23:    $k = k + 1$ 
24: end while

```

Algorithm 7 Full-Space Arnoldi Process for (1) with Preconditioner (2)

1: choose $[x_0; y_0]$ such that $Bx_0 - Cy_0 = 0$

2: initialize

$$\begin{bmatrix} v_{0,x} \\ v_{0,y} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

3: set

$$Bx_0 - Cy_0 = 0 \Rightarrow r_{0,y} = 0$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} r_{0,x} \\ r_{0,y} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} b \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} A & B^T \\ B & -C \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_0 \\ y_0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} b - Ax_0 - B^T y_0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

4: obtain v_1 as the solution of

$$\begin{bmatrix} G & B^T \\ B & -C \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_{1,x} \\ v_{1,y} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} r_{0,x} \\ r_{0,y} \end{bmatrix}$$

5: $h_{1,0} = (v_1^T r_0)^{\frac{1}{2}} = (v_{1,x}^T r_{0,x})^{\frac{1}{2}}$ 6: **if** $h_{1,0} \neq 0$ **then**7: $v_1 = v_1/\beta_1$ 8: **end if**9: $k = 1$ 10: **while** $h_{k,k-1} \neq 0$ **do**

11: compute

$$\begin{bmatrix} u_{k,x} \\ u_{k,y} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A & B^T \\ B & -C \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_{k,x} \\ v_{k,y} \end{bmatrix}$$

12: obtain v_{k+1} as the solution of

$$\begin{bmatrix} G & B^T \\ B & -C \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_{k+1,x} \\ v_{k+1,y} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} u_{k,x} \\ u_{k,y} \end{bmatrix}$$

13: **for** $i = 1, \dots, k$ **do**14: $h_{i,k} = v_i^T u_k = v_{i,x}^T A v_{k,x} + 2v_{i,x}^T B^T v_{k,y} - v_{i,y}^T C v_{k,y}$ 15: $v_{k+1} = v_{k+1} - h_{i,k} v_i$ 16: **end for**17: $h_{k+1,k} = (v_{k+1}^T u_k)^{\frac{1}{2}} = (v_{k+1,x}^T u_{k,x} + v_{k+1,y}^T u_{k,y})^{\frac{1}{2}}$ 18: **if** $h_{k+1,k} \neq 0$ **then**19: $v_{k+1} = v_{k+1}/h_{k+1,k}$ 20: **end if**21: $k = k + 1$ 22: **end while**
